

Disseminated Infective Endocarditis Presenting as Hypotension

Rinusha Rachel*

Pulmonologist, Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

Citation: Rinusha Rachel. Disseminated Infective Endocarditis Presenting as Hypotension. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2023;2(9):1-7.

Received Date: 8 March, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 13 March, 2023; **Published Date:** 18 March, 2023

***Corresponding author:** Rinusha Rachel, Pulmonologist, Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

Copyright: © Rinusha Rachel, Open Access 2023. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour (ICMCRJ)* (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

ABSTRACT

Infective endocarditis is a systemic infection with an enigmatic clinical presentation, which can delay diagnosis and treatment, resulting in a wide range of consequences. Despite advancements in treatment choices and antibiotics, appropriate management of infective endocarditis remains a formidable challenge. Male gender, advanced age, the existence of a prosthetic heart valve, and recreational intravenous drug use remain the primary risk factors for community-acquired infective endocarditis. As the infection is systemically pervasive, resulting in a variety of cardiac and extracardiac consequences, a multidisciplinary and multispecialty approach is essential for accomplishing optimal treatment outcomes.

Keywords: Infective endocarditis; Hypotension; Prosthetic heart valve

INTRODUCTION

Despite treatment, infectious endocarditis (IE) is a leading cause of mortality and morbidity across the globe. Owing to its rather ambiguous presentation, it can be difficult for clinicians to diagnose. We describe a dubious presentation of infective endocarditis as hypotension in a young man patient who is otherwise healthy.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 45-year-old male with history of alcohol use disorder was directed to present as Emergency department (ED) by the outpatient radiology department due to hypotension. The patient initially presented at outpatient radiology department for the X ray of his low back due to low back pain. He was noted to have a low blood pressure readings of about 90/56 mmHg prompting further evaluation in the ED. The hypotension was reaffirmed in the ED (92/62 mmHg), patient denied being on anti-hypertensive medications. On further questioning, reported feeling dizzy and lightheaded for one month prior to presentation. He also added that he had a recent tooth infection but otherwise denied any other recent illness/infection, sick contacts or travel. The patient reported that back pain also started about a month prior to presentation. He denied fevers, chills, night sweats but endorsed weight loss (15 pounds), fatigue and lethargy of 4-6 weeks duration. The patient reported drinking heavily in the past but had a recent inpatient acute alcohol rehabilitation and had been sober for at least one month prior to presentation. He denied history of liver cirrhosis, or hepatitis infection. The patient also denied other substance abuse including IV drug use. The patient reported going through a divorce and child custody legal battle and thought that was causing fatigue. Vitals on presentation were only remarkable for low blood pressure as mentioned above, but no fevers, tachypnea or tachycardia. The physical exam revealed a loud 3-4/6 systolic murmur over the aortic region. Initial blood work up showed leukocytosis with white cell count of $13.8 \times 10^3/\text{cmm}$ (reference range 4.30-10.80 $10^3/\text{cmm}$), hemoglobin 8.6 g/dl (reference range 14.0-18.0 mg/dL), platelet count $524 \times 10^3/\text{cmm}$ (reference range 150-400 $10^3/\text{cmm}$), creatinine was 1.0 mg/dL (reference range 0.9-1.30 mg/dL), C-reactive protein 198 mg/dL (reference range 0.0-1.0 mg/dL). Blood cultures were drawn, and he was empirically started on intravenous (IV) ceftriaxone and IV vancomycin. Due to the murmur and hypotension, IE was high in the differential, hence a transthoracic echocardiogram was obtained, which showed an ejection fraction of 60-65%, an echo density in the right coronary cusp of the aortic valve (AV) concerning for a vegetation (Figure 1) and moderate to severe AV insufficiency (Figure 2) along with AV perforation. Cardiology, cardiothoracic surgery and infectious disease were immediately consulted. The transthoracic echocardiogram findings were confirmed with a transesophageal echocardiogram (TEE) which also revealed 0.7 x 1.0 cm mass echo density on the right coronary cusp of AV with mild to moderate eccentric aortic regurgitation (AR/AI), AI maximum velocity (MV) 122.0 cm/sec and AI maximum peak gradient (MPG): 50.5 mmHg. A MRI of the lumbar spine was obtained due to low back pain concerning epidural abscess/discitis/osteomyelitis which did show a 2x2.2 cms L4 lumbar spine epidural abscess. The neurosurgery was consulted, and patient underwent prompt laminectomy and debridement of the abscess with local bone grafting, and a L5-S1 lumbar interbody fusion. Blood cultures grew pan sensitive *Streptococcus mitis*. Antibiotics were narrowed to IV ceftriaxone, repeat blood cultures were negative. The source of infection was infected tooth, and patient underwent immediate tooth extraction by oral maxillofacial surgery for source control. The patient also underwent AV repair for the severe aortic insufficiency and aortic valve small perforation by cardiothoracic surgery team. He had a left heart catheterization prior to the procedure which revealed normal coronaries. The patient received IV antibiotics for a total of 6 weeks duration and was doing well during his 3 months follow up.

Figure 1: Transthoracic Echocardiogram showed mobile vegetation attached to the Aortic valve.

Figure 2: TTE Image revealed moderate to severe aortic regurgitation.

DISCUSSION

Infective endocarditis is a prominent cause of morbidity and mortality that has a substantial effect on healthcare. Despite effective medical treatment, according to a 2009 systematic review, fatality rates from IE are approximately 25% ^[1]. One study found that 31% of culture-positive IE was caused by *Staphylococcus aureus*, 17% by viridians group streptococci, 11% by Enterococci, 7% by *Streptococcus Bovis*, and 5% by other *Streptococcus* ^[2]. Systematic review a decade later revealed that the rate of staphylococcal IE had grown in the United States, while the rate of IE caused by streptococcus viridans and culture-negative IE had dramatically decreased^[1]. The microbiologic profile of IE depends on the underlying risk factors^[3-31].

Immunosuppression, intravenous drug use, poor dental hygiene, degenerative valve disease, and rheumatic heart disease are all risk factors for developing community-acquired infections. Intravenous drug use, which accounts for around 10% of infectious endocarditis cases, suggests frequent inoculation with skin flora such as *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*, with *S. aureus* showing a preference for healthy, native tricuspid valves. During the course of its existence, this disease process has consistently shown a preference for males, with a male to female ratio that is nearly 2:1. Patients diagnosed with infective endocarditis now typically have an average age that is more than 65 years old. Its preponderance in the older population most likely corresponds to the greater frequency of predisposing variables within this

demographic, such as prosthetic valves, indwelling cardiac devices, acquired valvular disease, hemodialysis, and diabetes mellitus. Rheumatic heart disease used to be a prominent risk factor; but, in this day and age of antibiotics, it only accounts for a small percentage (less than 5 percent) of all cases. The use of intravenous drugs for recreational purposes is an increasing risk factor that is currently responsible for approximately 10% of all instances of infective endocarditis^[2].

Endocarditis can result in a multitude of intracardiac complications. Acute valvular incompetence can cause heart failure symptoms in about one-third of cases. This can happen as a result of an acute perforation of the valve or as a result of the chordae tendineae and papillary muscles becoming compromised. Regurgitation of the mitral or tricuspid valves can cause atrial enlargement and the subsequent development of atrial fibrillation and other supraventricular dysrhythmias. Intracardiac abscesses (14%) and atrioventricular blockages (8%), however, are much less common occurrences^[2].

Vegetations may detach from the heart valve, leading to a wide range of sequelae, including ischemic stroke, pulmonary infarct, splenic infarct, intracerebral hemorrhage, meningitis, and intracerebral abscess. The hematogenous dissemination of the infection may result in epidural abscess, discitis, osteomyelitis, perinephric abscess, pyelonephritis, and septic arthritis. The keys to preventing and effectively treating problems connected to IE are repeating blood cultures, controlling the source of the infection, and broadening the antibiotics promptly.

CONCLUSION

This case illustrates the significance of early diagnosis and treatment of life-threatening infective endocarditis, which have a very subclinical and vague presentation. To avoid the catastrophe associated with infectious endocarditis, prompt identification and treatment are crucial. In addition to increasing the risk of cardiac complications, bacteremia is associated with various systemic complications, such as epidural abscess in our instance. The importance of a multispecialty strategy in the optimal care of this multifaceted infection cannot be overstated.

REFERENCES

1. DeSimone DC, Wilson WR, Baddour LM. Trends in Infective Endocarditis Incidence, Microbiology, and Valve Replacement in the United States from 2000 to 2011. J Am Col Cardiol. 2015;66(10):1201-1202.
2. Murdoch DR. Clinical Presentation, Etiology, and Outcome of Infective Endocarditis in the 21st Century: The International Collaboration on Endocarditis–Prospective Cohort Study. Arch Intern Med. 2009;169(5):463-473.
3. Singh A, Singh D. Treadmill Exercise Stress Test-Induced Takotsubo Cardiomyopathy: A Case Report and Review of Literature. Cureus. 2023;15(1):e8715.
4. Bhatnagar UB, Singh D, Glazyrin A, Moormeier J. Paclitaxel induced MDS and AML: a case report and literature review. Case Rep Oncol Med. 2016;2016.

5. Elliott E, Watson T, Singh D, et al. Outcomes of specialty palliative care interventions for patients with hematologic malignancies: a systematic review. J Pain Symptom Manag. 2021; 62(4):863-875.
6. Grodzinsky A, Florio K, Spertus JA, Daming T, Lee J, Rader V, et al. Importance of the Cardio-Obstetrics Team. Curr Treat Options Cardio Med. 2019;21(12):84.
7. Jakhar I, Singh A, Yahia M, Sahil S, Singh D. The trend of spironolactone use in management of heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (hfpef). J Am Col Cardiol. 2022;79(9):526.
8. Knox B, Singh D, Mai H, Mirza K. Hodgkin's lymphoma with HLH and complete remission with brentuximab-based therapy. BMJ Case Reports CP. 2019;12(12):e231629.
9. Singh A, Ejaz A, Gunta PS, Jakulla RS, Singh D. Infective Endocarditis as a Complication of Crohn's Disease on Immunotherapy. Cureus. 2022;14(12):e32847.
10. Lehenbauer K, Qarajeh R, Shatla I, Singh A, Patel K, Peri-Okonny P, et al. Multimodality Imaging: Coronary Calcium Scoring And Myocardial Blood Flow Reserve To Predict Underlying Multivessel Coronary Artery Disease. J Cardiovasc Comp Tomograph. 2020;14(3):S64.
11. Singh A, Patel K, Patel F, Saxon JT, Grodzinsky A. An Overlooked Cause of Myocardial Infarction With Normal Coronaries Presenting as Stress Cardiomyopathy in Females. Cureus. 2023;15(1):e33251.
12. Madhusudhana S, Gates M, Singh D, Grover P, Indaram M, Cheng AL. Impact of psychological distress on treatment timeliness in oncology patients at a safety-net hospital. J Natl Compr Can Netw. 2021;1:e20058.
13. Singh A, O'keefe JH, Gersh F. Pharmaceutical Therapeutic Approaches to Reduce Cardiometabolic Risk in PCOS Women. J Obste Gynecol Rep. 2022;1:101.
14. Patel KK, Singh A, Bateman, TM. The Potential of F-18 Flurpiridaz PET/CT Myocardial Perfusion Imaging for Precision Imaging. Curr Cardiol Rep. 2022;24(8):987-994.
15. Patel K, Singh A, Peri-Okonny P, Patel F, Kennedy K, Lehenbauer K, et al. Importance of ischemia among asymptomatic patients with diabetes mellitus undergoing positron emission tomography (pet) myocardial perfusion imaging. J Am Col Cardiol. 2020;75(11 Supplement 1):1799.
16. Qarajeh R, Singh A, Khariton Y, Rafie N, Baweja P. Recurrent ST Elevation Myocardial Infarction from Norepinephrine-induced Coronary Vasospasm. Cureus. 2020;12(4):e7605.
17. Ros E, Singh A, O'Keefe JH. Nuts: Natural Pleiotropic Nutraceuticals. Nutrients. 2021;13(9):3269.
18. Singh A, Jakhar I, Singh D, Suman S, Gustavo D, Cheng AL, et al. Effects of bariatric surgery on atrial fibrillation recurrence rate post ablation. J Am Col Cardiol. 2022;79(9):159.

19. Vakiti A, Singh D, Pilla R, Alhaj-Moustafa M, Fitzpatrick KW. Bevacizumab-induced atypical hemolytic uremic syndrome and treatment with eculizumab. J Oncol Pharm Pract. 2019;25(4):1011-1015.
20. Singh D, Kapuria D, Nanua S, Gaur R. A case of de novo CD5+ disseminated intravascular large B-cell lymphoma presenting as multiorgan failure. Case Rep Hematol. 2016;2016: 6239416.
21. Singh D, Atieh MK, Russell MA, Kittaneh M. Malignant gastrointestinal neuroectodermal tumor (GNET) with prolonged disease-free survival after platinum-based chemotherapy. Case Rep Oncol Med. 2020;2020:1-5.
22. Singh A, Singh D. The Paleolithic Diet. Cureus. 2023;15(1):e34214.
23. Shrestha A, Grover P, Ahmed Z, Singh D, Arora S, Manthravadi S, et al. Clinical impact of iron overload on morbidity in patients with sickle cell disease. Blood. 2017;130(1):4787.
24. Singh A, Patel K, Florio K, Grodzinsky A, Schmidt LM. Management of multi-valvular left-sided stenotic lesions during pregnancy. J Am Col Cardiol. 2020;75(11):2340.
25. Singh A, Hardin BI, Singh D, Keyes D. Epidemiologic and Etiologic Considerations of Obesity. StatPearls Publishing, 2022.
26. Vakiti A, Padala SA, Singh D. Sezary syndrome. StatPearls Publishing, 2022.
27. Singh D, Natarajan A, Nand S, Mai HP. Genetics of hypercoagulable and hypocoagulable states. Neurosurg Clin N Am. 2018;29(4):493-501.
28. Vakiti A, Padala SA, Singh D. Cancer, Acute Myeloid Leukemia (AML, Erythroid Leukemia, Myelodysplasia-Related Leukemia, BCR-ABL Chronic Leukemia). StatPearls Publishing, 2020.
29. Berg S, Kim SH, Patel S, Rajakumar P, Elliott EJ, Schwartz C, et al. Real world outcomes of sars-Cov-2 thrombosis rates across three university health systems in the Chicago Metropolitan area. Blood. 2020;136:58-59.
30. Singh D, Hagen PA, Hossain N, Smith SE, Stiff PJ, Tsai SB. Liposomal Daunorubicin/Cytarabine As a Bridge to Second Allogeneic Transplant for Early Relapses after First Allograft for Acute Myelogenous Leukemia/Myelodysplastic Syndrome. Biol Blood Marrow Transplant. 2020; 26(3):S120-S121.
31. Strasser KM, Singh D, Graves J, Moormeier JA. Comparison of comorbidity to socioeconomic status in patients with non-small cell lung cancer in a safety net population.. J Clin Oncol. 2016;34(15):e18070.